

SKETCHING THE FOURIER TRANSFORM:
A GRAPHICAL PROCEDURE

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ABSTRACT

The spectrum signature of an electronic device is related to Fourier Transforms of its time-variant waveforms. Calculation of these transforms is time-consuming and often difficult.

By applying several useful properties of integrals and the known frequency spectrum of a chain of impulses, a method of simplifying the analysis is developed. It is easily committed to memory for rapid estimation of RFI from arbitrary waveforms, and is amenable to graphical solution. The method is of utility to technically inclined personnel who lack formal mathematical training, for no integrals appear in its "cook book" format.

An algorithm applicable to microprocessors or small computers is explored.

INTRODUCTION

Practicing engineers tend to shun the application of complex mathematics. In EMC work, this tendency surfaces in a reluctance to perform Fourier Transforms when investigating complex waveforms. As a result, the design engineer often glosses over the generation of radio frequencies which his device may later radiate as RFI.

The proper application of Fourier Transforms requires the solution of some often tedious integrals. The procedure is time consuming. Constraints of scheduling to meet a market demand often support the act of omitting this analysis.

The procedure given herein negates many of these problems. Fourier Transforms are reduced to a technique so simple that no integrals need be solved, nor is a computer required. The process can be completed in a "doodle" mode with nothing but pencil and paper.

The procedure can also be written as a simple algorithm for application on a micro-computer or programmable calculator. But its real utility remains its simplicity: it can be committed to memory. In a short time, the engineer becomes accustomed to viewing time-variant waveforms and performing "mental" trans-

forms on them. Significant radio frequencies can be "seen" on a time-display oscilloscope.

FOURIER SERIES

The procedure to be described has been dubbed a "Quick" transform. It differs in several regards from the "Fast" transform. To understand its development we will begin with a review of the conventional Fourier Expansion of repetitive waveforms.

Recall that cyclic waveforms can be expanded in an infinite series of sinusoids, the Fourier series, as follows: (Ref. 1)

$$f(t) = A_0 + \sum_1^{\infty} A_n \cos(n\omega t) + \sum_1^{\infty} B_n \sin(n\omega t) \quad (1)$$

The D.C. term, A_0 , is of no further interest and will be ignored.

The coefficients A_n and B_n are calculated thus:

$$A_n = \frac{W}{T} \int_t^{t+T} f(t) \cos(n\omega t) dt \quad (2)$$

$$B_n = \frac{W}{T} \int_t^{t+T} f(t) \sin(n\omega t) dt \quad (3)$$

The integrals are taken over one complete period of $f(t)$.

As a warm-up exercise, let's find the transform of a square wave defined by

$$f(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 < t \leq T/2 \\ 0, & T/2 < t \leq T \\ f(t+kT), & \text{everywhere} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

This waveform is shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1

Coefficients of the Fourier Series are found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_n &= \frac{w}{\pi} \int_0^T f(t) \cos(nwt) dt \\
 &= \frac{w}{\pi} \int_0^{T/2} 1 \cdot \cos(nwt) dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{w}{\pi} \int_{T/2}^T 0 \cdot \cos(nwt) dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{n\pi} \sin(n\pi/2) - \frac{1}{n\pi} \sin(0) \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

But $\sin(n\pi/2) = 0$, as $T/2$ is one-half period. Hence,

$A_n = 0$	for all n	(6)
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This reveals $f(t)$ to be an odd function, $f(t) = -f(-t)$. A glance at Figure 1 confirms the fact.

Now calculate the B_n :

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_n &= \frac{w}{\pi} \int_0^T f(t) \sin(nwt) dt \\
 &= \frac{w}{\pi} \int_0^{T/2} \sin(nwt) dt \\
 &= -\frac{w}{n\pi} \cos(nwt) \Big|_0^{T/2} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{n\pi} [\cos(n\pi/2) - 1] \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

The period T and frequency w are related by

$$w = 2\pi/T \quad (8)$$

so we can write

$$B_n = \frac{1}{n\pi} [1 - \cos(n\pi)] \quad (9)$$

For even (odd) values of n , $\cos(n\pi)$ is clearly equal to +1 (-1); so

$B_n = 2/n\pi$	n odd	(10)
$B_n = 0$	n even	(11)

Thus we obtain a familiar result, viz.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(t) &= \frac{2}{\pi} \left[\sin(wt) + \frac{1}{3} \sin(3wt) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{5} \sin(5wt) + \frac{1}{7} \sin(7wt) + \dots \right] \quad (12)
 \end{aligned}$$

A SPECIAL FUNCTION

There is a function repetitive in time that has a most curious and useful property. Consider an impulse, which is everywhere zero save at one time, t_0 . It can be defined by

$$d(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & , \quad t \neq t_0 \\ \infty & , \quad t \rightarrow t_0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

This function becomes infinite at $t=t_0$. However, it does so in a controlled fashion, such that it satisfies

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{t_0-\epsilon}^{t_0+\epsilon} d(t) dt = 1 \quad (14)$$

The special periodic function we seek is a chain of such impulses, defined by

$$f(t) = d(t+kT) \quad \text{for all integer } k \quad (15)$$

so that, for any k ,

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{t_0+kT-\epsilon}^{t_0+kT+\epsilon} f(t) dt = 1. \quad (16)$$

This function has the form shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2

The arrows indicate a pulse height of zero width but infinite height.

Think of $f(t)$ as a train of rectangular pulses of constant area. As their width decreases, their height increases without limit. Figure 2 results in the limit of zero width.

A straightforward Fourier Transform of $f(t)$ can be performed. Coefficients A_n are found as usual:

$$A_n = \frac{w}{\pi} \int_0^T f(t) \cos(nwt) dt \quad (17)$$

But $f(t)$ is zero everywhere save near t_0 . Therefore we can break (17) into three integrals.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_n &= \frac{w}{\pi} \int_0^{t_0-\epsilon} 0 \cdot \cos(nwt) dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{w}{\pi} \int_{t_0-\epsilon}^{t_0+\epsilon} f(t) \cos(nwt) dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{w}{\pi} \int_{t_0+\epsilon}^T 0 \cdot \cos(nwt) dt \quad (18)
 \end{aligned}$$

The first and third of these vanish, leaving only the second integral to be evaluated.

Now, if epsilon is chosen sufficiently small, $\cos(nwt)$ will remain (essentially) constant over the range of integration. We may consider it a constant, an approximation that improves without limit as epsilon shrinks. We obtain

$$A_n = \frac{w}{\pi} \cos(nwt_0) \int_{t_0 - \epsilon}^{t_0 + \epsilon} f(t) dt$$

$$= \frac{w}{\pi} \cos(nwt_0) \quad (19)$$

By choice of the origin of time we may set $t_0 = 0$ without loss of generality. Then

$$A_n = \frac{w}{\pi} \quad \text{for all values of } n. \quad (20)$$

We have found a frequency comb! Each harmonic has exactly the same amplitude. This well-known result surprises some people.

The reader may perform an entirely similar analysis with sine integrals to obtain the other result,

$$B_n = 0 \quad \text{for all values of } n. \quad (21)$$

The spectrum of the impulse is simple. Memorize it. The Quick Transform is rooted in this relationship.

A USEFUL TRICK

The results derived above will be needed shortly. We diverge to explore another property of Fourier Series.

Suppose we have a periodic function $f(t)$ whose transform is unknown. Suppose further that we know the transform of $f'(t)$, its derivative. The two transforms are related.

The relationship is obtained by expanding $f'(t)$ in a Fourier Series. From equation (1),

$$f'(t) = A'_0 + \sum_1^{\infty} A'_n \cos(nwt)$$

$$+ \sum_1^{\infty} B'_n \sin(nwt) \quad (22)$$

By definition,

$$f(t) = \int f'(t) dt \quad (23)$$

so

$$f(t) = A'_0 t + \int \sum_1^{\infty} A'_n \cos(nwt) dt$$

$$+ \int \sum_1^{\infty} B'_n \sin(nwt) dt \quad (24)$$

from which it follows that

$$f(t) = A'_0 t + \sum_1^{\infty} A'_n \int \cos(nwt) dt$$

$$+ \sum_1^{\infty} B'_n \int \sin(nwt) dt \quad (25)$$

$$f(t) = A'_0 t + \sum_1^{\infty} -\frac{B'_n}{nw} \cos(nwt)$$

$$+ \sum_1^{\infty} \frac{A'_n}{nw} \sin(nwt) \quad (26)$$

Thus the series for $f(t)$ has coefficients given by

$$A_n = -(B'_n / nw) \quad (27)$$

$$B_n = (A'_n / nw) \quad (28)$$

From equations (27) and (28) we observe the following facts on integration of a time-periodic waveform:

- 1) Every harmonic in the spectrum has its amplitude modified by the factor $1/w$.
- 2) Every harmonic further has its amplitude modified by the factor $1/n$. That is, its amplitude is reduced by its harmonic number.
- 3) Each cosine and sine term of $f'(t)$ is retarded in phase by 90° .

ADDITIONAL PROPERTIES OF INTEGRALS

Two remaining properties of integrals that are then properties of Fourier Transforms are required for our continuing analysis. These are:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \int_a^c f(x) dx + \int_c^b f(x) dx \quad (29)$$

where $a \leq c \leq b$, and

$$\int (f_1(x) + f_2(x)) dx =$$

$$\int f_1(x) dx + \int f_2(x) dx \quad (30)$$

These relations are easily verified. Recall the fundamental theorem of integral calculus which states that

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx = \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \sum_a^b f(x_i) \Delta x_i \quad (31)$$

An integral is simply the sum of many infinitesimally small terms, and the value of a sum is independent of the order in which terms are added.

A GRAPHICAL APPROACH TO FOURIER ANALYSIS

The focus of this paper is demonstrating that the integrals of the preceding pages are unnecessary. One may establish the spectrum of periodic waveforms by graphical constructs alone.

Reconsider now the square wave of Figure 1. Could one guess the spectral content of this waveform at a glance? Probably not - at least not yet. True, the fundamental frequency is obvious, and one supposes that many harmonics exist.

The Quick Transform procedure requires that the waveform be converted to impulse functions. Let us sketch the time derivative of the square wave. The dual set of delta functions as in Figure 4 result.

Equation (30) permits us to divide this waveform into two separate functions, the positive spikes and the negative spikes. Analysis is performed on each set separately. Resulting spectra are then summed to obtain the spectrum of Figure 4.

Analysis of the positive-going chain is simple. We have already done so, and memorized the result that all frequencies are present and of the same amplitude. Further, each cosine wave is phased to have a maximum at the position of the spike. This result is tabulated in Table I.

TABLE I
HARMONIC ANALYSIS

Harmonic number	1	2	3	4	5	6	etc.
Amplitude	1	1	1	1	1	1	etc.

The first chain of delta functions has now been considered. Remove it from the picture - literally, erase it from Figure 4 - and analyze

the remaining residue. This is permitted by equation (30).

The residue is itself a chain of delta functions. However, these differ from the first chain in two respects: they are negative spikes, and their timing varies by one-half cycle from the first chain. Their frequency spectrum is nonetheless the same: a fundamental and all harmonics of the same amplitude. Note that the step giving rise to the negative chain is the same in amplitude as that giving rise to the positive spikes. That is, the integral across either a positive or negative spike has the same magnitude. Therefore, relative amplitudes of the two spectra are identical.

Now expand Table I to include the negative spikes. Table II results.

TABLE II
HARMONIC ANALYSIS

Harmonic number	1	2	3	4	5	6	etc
Amplitude 1	1	1	1	1	1	1	etc
Amplitude 2	1	1	1	1	1	1	etc
position ϕ	180	360	180	360	180	360	etc
time ϕ	180	180	180	180	180	180	etc
total ϕ	0	180	0	180	0	180	etc
Grand Total							
Amplitude	2	0	2	0	2	0	etc
Phase	0	-	0	-	0	-	etc

What is the significance of these new entries? Let's take them one at a time.

The negative chain of spikes produces harmonics whose amplitudes, relative to the first chain's harmonics, are listed as "Amplitude 2." But this chain is positioned in time one-half cycle late compared to the first chain. Thus, each harmonic is delayed by one-half period at the fundamental frequency, a constant time. Therefore, the fundamental suffers a 180 degree phase shift, the second harmonic suffers a 360 degree shift (the delay time is constant) and so on. These shifts are shown as "position ϕ ."

The second chain of spikes is negative. This causes each cosine-wave in its spectrum to be negative, too - they must all add to produce the spike. Thus each harmonic in the spectrum is a negative cosine wave, and is shifted 180 degrees as a result. These shifts are recorded in the row marked "time ϕ ." The shift is exactly 180 degrees for each harmonic, and is not dependent on harmonic number.

The total phase of each harmonic is the sum of the position and time phase shifts. These results are recorded in the "total ϕ " row.

We are now in a position to generate the complete spectrum of Figure 4. We add vectorially the "Amplitude 1" and "Amplitude 2" components. The phase of Amplitude 1 is always zero, for we chose time to be initiated at the position of the first chain of spikes, which we chose as a positive chain. The vector sum of spectral components is tabulated in the rows "Grand Total Amplitude" and "Grand Total Phase."

The last two rows of Table II give us the spectrum of Figure 4's waveform. But we want the spectrum of Figure 1, a square wave. Recall now equations (27) and (28). What is required is the 90 degree retardation of each component of the spectrum, and a $1/n$ reduction of the amplitude of the n -th harmonic. The spectrum of a square wave then follows. It contains:

- * A fundamental of 2 relative units amplitude.
- * A third harmonic of $2/3$ relative units.
- * A fifth harmonic of $2/5$ relative units.
- etc.

Compare this result with equation (12). Qualitatively, they are identical.

THE QUICK TRANSFORM

We now have a handy method of doing Fourier Analysis without resorting to integrals! The procedure can be condensed to a "cook-book" recipe. It is:

- THE QUICK TRANSFORM
- 1) Sketch the time-variant waveform.
 - 2) If it contains no spikes, sketch its time derivative.
 - 3) Continue sketching derivatives until spikes appear. Record the highest order of derivative sketched as " m ."
 - 4) In tabular form record the relative amplitude and phase of each harmonic, using the known spectral property of delta function chains.
 - 5) Add spectral components of the table vectorially.
 - 6) Divide the n -th harmonic's amplitude by $n^m \cdot 2\pi/T$ for each harmonic.
 - 7) Retard the n -th harmonic's phase by $n \cdot 90^\circ$ for each harmonic.
 - 8) Remove the spikes from the sketch. If a residue remains, continue this procedure.

A TACIT EXAMPLE

FIGURE 5A

FIGURE 5B

FIGURE 5C (Proceed to Table V)

FURTHER OBSERVATIONS

One may note that the Quick Transform does not always work. In fact, a large class of functions exist such that no derivative produces spikes. Consider the sine wave, for example. Does the Quick Transform, then, have application only in certain situations? Seemingly so.

Consider, though, a "smooth" function - one whose derivatives of all order exist. A type as in Figure 6 might satisfy this constraint. Figure 6 also demonstrates the result of a "step and hold" sampling circuit at work on the function. This waveform is an ideal candidate for the Quick Transform.

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

TABLE V
HARMONIC ANALYSIS OF FIGURE 5

Harmonic number	1	2	3	4	5	6 etc.
<u>m = 1</u> components of f'(t)						
Amplitude (c)	3	3	3	3	3	3 etc.
position ϕ	3/4	6/4	9/4	12/4	15/4	18/4
time ϕ	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2
total ϕ	1/4	0	3/4	2/4	1/4	0
Amplitude (d)	1	1	1	1	1	1 etc.
position ϕ	4/4	8/4	12/4	16/4	20/4	24/4
time ϕ	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2
total ϕ	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2
<u>m = 2</u> components of f''(t)						
Amplitude (a)	8	8	8	8	8	8 etc.
position ϕ	0	0	0	0	0	0
time ϕ	0	0	0	0	0	0
total ϕ	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amplitude (b)	8	8	8	8	8	8 etc.
position ϕ	2/4	4/4	6/4	8/4	10/4	12/4
time ϕ	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2
total ϕ	0	1/2	0	1/2	0	1/2
<u>m = 1</u> components of f''(t) divide by $w = 2\pi/T = 2\pi$ divide by n delay ϕ by 1/4 cycle						
Amplitude (a)	1.27	.637	.424	.318	.255	.212
total ϕ	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4	1/4
Amplitude (b)	1.27	.637	.424	.318	.255	.212
total ϕ	1/4	3/4	1/4	3/4	1/4	3/4
From above,						
Amplitude (c)	3	3	3	3	3	3
total ϕ	1/4	0	3/4	1/2	1/4	0
Amplitude (d)	1	1	1	1	1	1
total ϕ	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2	1/2
VECTOR SUM	5.63	2	2.37	4	3.65	2
<u>m = 0</u> divide by 2π ; divide by n						
VECTOR SUM	.896	.159	.126	.159	.116	.053

We may sketch the stepwise approximation to obtain its derivative, Figure 7. Although each spike is infinite, they have been drawn to a scale indicative of the magnitude of their integral.

The transform of Figure 7 is obvious. Each spike may be treated separately, and terms added to a table of harmonic analysis. When all spikes have been accommodated, it is necessary only to sum vectorially the terms in the table, divide each harmonic amplitude by its harmonic number, and retard each phase shift by 1/4 cycle. One derivative is all that is needed, as no residue exists after the above analysis.

EXPLORING AN ALGORITHM

The discussion above suggests a simple and general algorithm. A Fourier Series expansion, itself an approximation to a Fourier Transform, could be computed quickly as follows.

GENERAL ALGORITHM
THE QUICK TRANSFORM

- 1) Approximate the function in a "step and hold" format.
- 2) Differentiate this approximation. Label each spike with its integral's amplitude.
- 3) Construct a table of harmonic analysis. Enter therein the contributions of each spike.
- 4) Vectorially add all harmonic contributions.
- 5) Divide each amplitude by the harmonic number.
- 6) Shift each harmonic's phase by -90° .

At this writing such algorithms are being explored for application on various small systems including the MC6800 microprocessor.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It is hoped that the non-integral method of sketching Fourier Transforms, or more accurately, Fourier Expansions, will be of assistance. Math has been reduced to a matter of addition.

The method, while possessing shortcomings, allows rapid pencil-and-paper analysis differing little from "doodling." If we must doodle, it may as well be useful.

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